

Corrosion Potential of Soil-metal Systems in Corrosion Cells

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Studies have been made of the variations in the anode and the cathode potentials, with increasing current under applied potential, of the electrodes in the corrosion cell for a particular combination of soil and electrode materials. For this purpose, soils collected from selected spots on the Durgapur—Calcutta route (viz., Durgapur, Burdwan, Saktigarh, Chinsura, and Shibpur), cast iron (C.I.) (C, 3.1%; Si, 2.09%; Mn, 0.91%; S, 0.12%; P, 0.27%), and mild steel (C, 0.28%; Si, 0.08%; Mn, 0.91%; S, 0.04%; P, 0.03%) have been used.

The details of the corrosion cell of Denison type, as used in these experiments, have been reported in previous publications^{1,2}. A brief outline of the corrosion cell assembly is, however, given here for ready reference. The corrosion cell consists of a cathode of ferrous materials, referred to above, in the form of a perforated disc, separated by a layer of moist soil from the anode of the same material in the form of a solid disc as the cathode. The cell is so assembled that the perforated cathode is more accessible to air than the solid anode. The electrodes are kept short circuited. The cell current is measured with a zero resistance micro-ammeter without permitting the cell to be on open circuit. Increasing potentials were applied to the electrodes using dry cells and an adjustable rheostat. The electrode potentials were measured using a Vernier Cambridge potentiometer, a multiflex galvanometer, and a saturated calomel half-cell as a reference electrode.

The data so far obtained on the variation of the cathode and anode potential-current density are shown in Fig. 1. The polarisation at the anode is found to be more than that at the cathode of the respective corrosion cell except in the case of Chinsura soil and mild steel electrodes. It appears³ therefore that in most of the cases studied, the reactions at the anode dominate to a greater extent the rate and nature of corrosion reaction taking place inside the cell than at the cathode. The intersection of the anode potential-current density and cathode potential-current density curves gives the corrosion potential⁴ of the particular combination of soil and the electrode material. The current at this potential represents the current at which maximum corrosion takes place. The

1. Chatterjee and Gupta, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1959, 22, 159.
2. Roy, Sarkar, and Chatterjee, *ibid.*, 1961, 24, 113.
3. Romanoff, U. S. Bur. Stds., Circular 1957, No. 570, p. 160.
4. Evans, *J. Franklin Inst.*, 1920, 208, 45.

corrosion potential, maximum cell current, current at corrosion potential, and the weight losses of the electrodes, exposed to the soil in the corrosion cell for six months, are shown in Table I.

FIG. 1

The data presented in Table I show lack of any correlation of the maximum short circuit current and of current at corrosion potential with weight losses of the electrodes. A better correlation has, however, been obtained between the corrosion potential and the combined weight loss of the anodes and cathodes. A more or less linear relationship (Fig. 2) has been obtained between the corrosion potential and the combined weight losses of the electrodes, e.g., the higher the corrosion potential (-ve), the higher is the weight loss.

TABLE I

Soils.	Depth.	Specimen.	Corrosion potential volts (-ve) (H-scale)	Current at corrosion potential (μ A).	Maximum short circuit current (μ A).	Loss in wt. of electrodes ($g./cm^2$).
Chinsura	2 ft.	C.I.	0.408	92	71	
		M.S.	0.510	70	00	0.074
Saktigarh	,,	C.I.	0.515	30	1	0.077
		M.S.	0.513	45	8	0.056
Burdwan	,,	C.I.	0.518	50	36	0.066
		M.S.	0.503	60	40	0.077
Durgapur	,,	C.I.	0.461	134	70	0.057
		M.S.	0.448	150	64	0.043
Shibpur	8 ft.	C.I.	0.505	55	55	0.039
		M.S.	0.518	60	18	0.037
						0.024

FIG. 2

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